

Notes on service portfolio requirements

Supplement to “Base4NFDI service integration procedures”
<https://zenodo.org/records/15235863>

Version 2, September 2025

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Overview

The future service portfolio will include all services that have successfully completed the Integration Phase. There will be a catalogue that makes it possible to search and find information about the services and that provides information about access to and use of a particular service. To this end, each included service must fulfil a set of standardised requirements, represented by a list of metadata to be provided. Most of these are short snippets of information, others must be selected from a range of alternatives, and a few require a short concept. Especially for the latter, Base4NFDI will provide guides and templates the service teams can utilise.

General considerations

The requirements for admission of a service to the portfolio are based on these premises:

1. There must be **as few requirements as possible**.
2. The service **teams must be able to fulfil them** during the Initialisation, Integration, and Ramp-Up Phases, respectively.
3. **Sign-off requirements** of a phase **must automatically serve as starting conditions** of the subsequent phase, **without any additional requirements** in between.
4. The requirements must be **consistent** with what is needed by especially EOSC.

This set of standards can be grouped into 7 categories of increasing complexity:

1. **General:** service documentation, hosting institution, ...
2. **Contact:** service owner, 1st level support, ...
3. **Conditions:** service quality, offerings, limitations, ...
4. **Users:** authentication, enablement, ...
5. **Security:** data protection, backup strategy, security incident contact, ...
6. **Legal:** processing of personal data, GDPR compliance, charges, privacy policy, ...
7. **KPIs and operation concept**

Base4NFDI is developing an electronic form for entering and keeping track of any related content, and TA2 staff and Service Stewards will actively assist the service team in mapping their own deliverables to the requirements presented here.

Details

In what follows, the requirements are listed in the order of relevance for the three Base4NFDI phases:

- Apart from some requirements given at the very end, all requirements are mandatory.
- For each requirement, the respective category (see above) is given in brackets (“[...]”)
- Some information is required **only conditionally** and is marked accordingly.
- Possible relations to the EOSC interoperability requirements¹ are indicated as well (“EOSC”).
- A short sentence explains what the service teams are expected to do.
- In some cases, there are **mandatory values**.

¹ “Guidelines for Onboarding Resources to EOSC Exchange”, sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2 (<https://zenodo.org/records/10621226>) - fulfilment of these means basic interoperability with EOSC

In general, all information needs to be there at the end of the respective phase, but it can be collected at any time before whenever it becomes available. Very few topics are relevant for the application for the Ramp-Up Phase and should be addressed by month 18 of the Integration Phase (marked “M18” below).

Sign-off of initialisation

Service name, [general]

EOSC

Provide a meaningful name for the service

Short description, [general]

EOSC

Provide an one-liner to appear in the service catalogue

Service owner, [contact] - M18

EOSC: technical contact

Provide name and mail address of the person responsible for the service at the hosting institution

Service uses IAM4NFDI, [users]

EOSC: access policies

Confirm that the service employs IAM4NFDI

required value = yes, if the service requires authentication/authorisation

Non-profit, [legal]

Confirm that the service is provided on a non-profit basis

required value = yes

Ad-free, [legal]

Confirm that the service is provided without advertisements

required value = yes

Sign-off of integration

Long description, [general]

EOSC

Provide a description of the service, its functionalities, and other relevant information for the potential service users – max. one page.

Keywords/tags/categories, [general]

EOSC

From a provided list of service-specific categories choose those that apply to the service.

Link to service documentation, [general]

EOSC: website, resource assets, manual

Provide a link to any further and more detailed documentation of the service: access, user manual, training resources, ...

Link to hosted service, [general]

EOSC: URL to resource

Provide a link for accessing the service at the site providing it.

Imprint of hosting institution, [general]

EOSC: organisation name and address

Provide a link to the imprint of the institution providing the service.

Service publication consent, [general] - M18

The hosting institution must formally consent to have the service published - confirm.

required value = yes

Involved consortia, [general]

EOSC: affiliated organisations, network

Provide a list of the consortia involved in the development or provision of the service or in the service team.

Services dependencies, [general]

EOSC: related platforms/resources

Describe/list on which other services this service relies or for which it is required.

Service manager, [contact] - M18

EOSC: administrative contact

Provide name and mail address of the service owner's supervisor.

1st level support contact, [contact]

EOSC: helpdesk contact

Describe how to access 1st level support at the hosting institution – can be either of name and mail address of the responsible person, the url of their ticket system, or the mail address of the latter.

Description of contact with portfolio management, [contact]

Describe how the hosting institution will communicate with the Base4NFDI portfolio management: by mail, ticket system, chat, ... whatever.

Description of service offerings, [conditions]

EOSC: terms of use, maintenance information

If applicable, describe the provided service offerings, e. g., availability % p.a., support times, reaction times, maintenance time slots, regular updates, ...

Description of limitations, [conditions]

EOSC: performance expectations

If applicable, describe the maximum resources provided for individual service instances and/or overall service, e. g., data volume, cpu hours, ...

Description of tangible kpis, [operation concept / KPIs]

Describe the indicators that are used for monitoring service usage.

Drafted operation concept, [operation concept / KPIs]

Compile the expected technical, personnel, and financial resources required to run the service.

Description of user enablement, [users]

EOSC: access mechanisms

Describe any registration and authorisation steps necessary for users to access and actually use the service.

Description of fees, [legal]

EOSC: pricing, payment model

Indicate whether there are charges for service usage or not. If so, describe how these are calculated.

Security incident contact, [security]

EOSC: security contact

Provide details of whom to contact in case of security incidents, and how.

Service location, [security] - M18

EOSC: geographic location

Indicate where the service or its components are running: Germany, EU, ...

Sign-off of ramp-up

GDPR-compliance, [legal]

EOSC: privacy policy

If the service uses personal data, confirm – for each provider involved – their compliance with GDPR.

required value = yes

Description of personal data processing / storage, [legal]

EOSC: privacy policy

If the service uses personal data, describe – for each provider involved – how personal data are processed and protected, including relevant TOMs and VTs.

Description of service/data privacy policy, [security]

EOSC: privacy policy

Describe – for each provider involved – how service/data privacy is maintained, including relevant TOMs and VTs.

Description of data security, protection, and backup, [security]

EOSC: privacy policy

If applicable, describe the data protection and backup measures in place: weekly, geo-redundant.

Business model, [operation concept / KPIs]

Finalise the business model of the service, describe the organisational form, the costs, and how it will be sustainably funded.

Non-mandatory but helpful

Web site of hosting institution, [general]

Provide the according URL

ID of hosting institution, [general]

Provide the registered ID of the institution, e. g. , ROR

Description of service enablement, [users]

EOSC: access mechanisms

Describe any IT components which might be required at the user's side, e. g., clients, software libraries